

Do as You Like:

Free Will and Reconciliation in *Þórðar saga hreðu*

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Introduction of the Themes

Norse literature, one of the most popular mythological frameworks, is well known for several themes and properties. Fate very often plays an important role in the sagas; the burning of Njál in *Bergthórshvál* or Sigurd's betrayal of Brynhild are examples of this. Their decided path ends in tragedy, and they cannot escape it; they may try, but they always fail.¹ Another of these common themes is revenge; *Hrafnkels saga freysgoða* is about a disgraced priest who punishes those who wronged him, and *Færeyinga saga* is about an orphan that seeks vengeance against his father's murderers.

But despite this, a saga called *Þórðar saga hreðu* (commonly translated as '*The Saga of Thórðr the Terror*') contains themes which are both philosophically libertarian and humanist; it is an antithesis to the other works. The saga exists in two distinct manuscripts, one fragmentary and one complete. This essay will concern the complete version because it has much more information about the manuscript and the story; attempting to analyze the incomplete version would be an exercise in futility as it is extremely difficult to make an accurate thesis concerning an incomplete work. The complete version, believed to be transcribed in the bishopric of Hólar around c. 1420 C.E. about events in the 900s, follows the life of a Norwegian poet, warrior, and carpenter known as 'Thórðr Hreða' for whom the saga is named.² This essay seeks to understand the peculiar themes of free will and reconciliation this saga contains and to highlight the implications which they have on our understanding of the Norse people.

The saga has been largely unpopular in the academic community for several reasons.

These are generally chalked up to be four things: 1) a weak narrative arc, 2) the lack of a tragic

¹ Tom Griffith, ed., *Njál's Saga*, trans. Carl F. Bayerschmidt and Lee M. Hollander (Ware, Hertfordshire: Wordsworth Classics of World Literature, 1998), 253; William Morris and Eiríkr Magnússon, trans., "The Saga of the Völsungs," in *The Norse Sagas, Part 1*, vol. 4 (1888; repr., Pounding Mill, VA: Henderson Publishing, 2024), 41.

² H Friðriksson, trans., *Sagan Af Þórði Hreðu*, vol. VI (Copenhagen: Brødrene Berlings Bogtrykkeri, 1848); Elizabeth Ward, "Completing Þórðr Saga Hreðu: A Regional Saga in Disguise," *Gripla* 27, no. 1 (2016), 93-5 <https://tinyurl.com/hd4eakex>.

element, 3) a near-complete absence of legal activity, and 4) no ‘fate-agent’.³ These criticisms are correct. But even so, they do not represent narrative flaws; they are instead symptoms of the diverse philosophy that this work supports. The lack of fate is not indicative of poor writing but instead shows the contemporarily unique worldview of the author, displaying his libertarian beliefs; the happy ending, which is used by the author to show his support of the themes, is responsible for both the first and second criticisms.

Þórðar saga hreðu contains a specific ‘thematic refrain’⁴ which appears a number of times throughout the text; the context of when it is used is proof of the author’s philosophy, as it is deployed with care on each occasion. This refrain *mantu eigi göra, sem þér líkar* roughly translates to English as ‘Will/may you not do as you like?’⁵ While the translation appears simple enough on the surface, an understanding of Norse linguistic culture reveals layers of complexity. For example, the use of the word *mantu* (the second person singular present tense form of the word *muna*, meaning ‘remember to do’) gives the impression that their will is almost an inevitability; their freedom to act of their own accord is inherent to the human condition.

To fully understand the author’s worldview, several uses of it must be understood; as there are multiple different outcomes between the usages of the phrase, multiple case studies of the most instructive examples must be performed. The phrase occurs ten times throughout the saga (six times explicitly and four times indirectly), forcing this essay to disregard repetitive uses; only three occasions will be explored, with the rest serving as corroborating evidence for this interpretation. The omitted cases will be listed in the following footnote for the reader to examine on their own.

³ Ibid.

⁴ It is referred to as a ‘thematic refrain’ rather than a ‘quote’ because the exact wording changes.

⁵ Richard Cleasby and Guðbrandur Vigfússon, *An Icelandic-English Dictionary* (Clarendon Press, 1874), under “Ei-Gi”, “Munu”, “Göra”, “Sem”, “Þér”, and “Líka,” <https://tinyurl.com/mx33vcu9>.

On Fatalism

In c. 961 C.E., upon Thórðr's arrival in Miðfjörðr after fleeing Norway to escape King Harald Greycloak, he meets a man called Eyjúlfr who is a farmer under the chieftain Skeggi.⁶ Eyjúlfr introduces himself to Thórðr and offers to ask Skeggi whether he would allow Thórðr to stay with him over the winter. Thórðr is against this, but gives way. Here occurs the first example of the refrain.⁷ When Eyjúlfr brings this point to Skeggi, he replies that although Thórðr is an honorable man, he will not take him to stay over the winter; Eyjúlfr thus allows Thórðr to live at his own abode at Ós during the winter.

While this negative outcome seems at first to be a counterpoint to the thematic narrative that I have outlined throughout this essay, a closer examination will reveal this quote's deeper meaning. In other sagas, Skeggi is shown to be hospitable to newcomers; this is shown in *Kormák's saga* when he gives land to a man called Ogmund who is of less importance and wealth than Thórðr.⁸ So why, then, was Thórðr refused? This is very likely due to Thórðr's status as a fugitive of King Harald Greycloak; Skeggi, a smart man, would likely wish to avoid a confrontation with the king for harboring a fugitive. While Harald Greycloak never comes to hunt Thórðr down, it would be a reasonable fear as Thórðr's crime (helping to kill Harald's brother Sigurðr Slefa) was unusually extreme. It may also be doubted whether the news of Thórðr's crime would have arrived before him; but Thórðr leaves some time after Harald learns of this and takes an indirect path.⁹ A merchant ship, going directly to Iceland, would almost certainly have arrived before him. It is therefore safe to assume that without the pleading of Eyjúlfr, Skeggi would have reacted with immediate enmity; the callous indifference he exhibits

⁶ Snorri Sturluson, "Heimskringla," Project Gutenberg, November 27, 2009, <https://tinyurl.com/7ymbct5v>.

⁷ Friðriksson, *Sagan af Þórði Hreðu*, p. 9.

⁸ Jón Stefánsson and William Collingwood, trans., "The Life and Death of Cormac the Skald," in *The Norse Sagas, Part 3*, vol. 6 (1902; repr., Pounding Mill, VA: Henderson Publishing, 2024), 62.

⁹ John Coles, trans., "The Saga of Thórðr Hreða," in *The Norse Sagas, Part 1*, vol. 4 (1882; repr., Pounding Mill, VA: Henderson Publishing, 2024), 318-20.

is an act of mercy rather than one of spite.¹⁰ Because the interaction would likely have gone much differently if Eyjúlfr was not present to acquaint the two, it can be safely assumed that the author is here helping Thórðr because he ‘approves’ of his action. This practice of a character receiving a positive outcome after making a certain decision will be called ‘reward’ for the rest of the essay. ‘Punishment’ will be used to denote the opposite.

The second noteworthy occurrence of this phrase appears shortly after, when two farmers called Jón and Auðúlfr are talking about an expensive coat. Auðúlfr wishes to buy it for his sister, but Jón is against it due to the exorbitant cost; but eventually, as Auðúlfr debates with him, Jón relents. Here occurs the second appearance of the thematic refrain; although the wording here changes, the meaning does not.¹¹ They leave briefly to fetch the price of the coat, but in their absence Thórðr and his foster-son Eiðr (son of Skeggi) buy the coat for his sister instead. When Auðúlfr and Jón return, they make the decision to attack Thórðr for the coat; Eiðr enlists Skeggi’s help to kill the two.¹² While Jón appears to be punished for using the phrase, this is not the case; here, the author is providing nuance to his philosophy for the purpose of ‘teaching’ the audience.

In this example, the author deliberately ruined Jón and Auðúlfr due to the poor choices that they made; they were punished while Thórðr and Eyjúlfr were praised primarily due to two reasons. The first of these is intent; Guðrún (Auðúlfr’s sister) is called *oflátí*, which translates to ‘vain or showy’ and was regarded negatively by Viking society.¹³ While the motivations of Eyjúlfr were good, the motivations of Guðrún (channeled through Auðúlfr) were not, which contributed to their punishment. The second of these two factors is violence; while Eyjúlfr acted

¹⁰ Ibid, 320-1.

¹¹ Friðriksson, *Sagan af Þórði Hreðu*, 18.

¹² Coles, “The Story of Thórðr Hreða,” 326-8.

¹³ Ibid; Cleasby and Vigfússon, *An Icelandic-English Dictionary*, under “Of-látí”.

calmly and proceeded in a level-headed manner after Skeggi refused him, Jón and Auðúlfr attempted to murder Thórðr. This sharp contrast between Eyúlfr's collected demeanor and Auðúlfr's immediate rage shows why they were punished. In terms of the author's philosophy, this is a quite instructive example as it provides nuance for his viewpoint; in Jón and Auðúlfr's punishment, two distinct lessons are learned about the author's beliefs. The passage shows that intent matters; he argues that his philosophy does not call for the resignation of ideals, as Jón compromised his own. He also recognizes the blurry line between freedom and anarchy, highlighting the difference between the two.

The fourth case (the third¹⁴ is omitted because it is extremely similar to the first) is particularly interesting, as it directly displays the author's disdain of fatalism. In this situation, Skeggi's nephew Ormr comes to Miðfjörðr and sees Sigríðr, Thórðr's sister. He asks Skeggi to obtain her hand in marriage, but he refuses because she is already betrothed to Ormr's brother Ásbjörn. Ormr, smitten, corners Sigríðr alone as she is washing linen and forcefully lays his head in her lap. This exchange follows: “Því at þetta er á móti mínum vilja; eða mantu eigi ályktarorð bróður míns? ok man hann þat efna; sjá þú svá fyrir þínum hluta.’ Hann segir: ‘Ekki hirði ek um grýlur yðrar.’”¹⁵ Translated, it is this: “[Sigríðr says,] ‘For this is against my will; or mindset thou not the last words of threats of my brother’s, which he will be only too sure to keep, so you had better see to your affairs.’ [Ormr] answers: ‘I am not going to be frightened at your bogey-men.’” Thórðr soon finds out and kills Ormr.¹⁶

Ormr's dismissal of Sigríðr's brothers as 'bogey-men' is shocking; the brothers of Sigríðr are known for their prowess and are more than enough of a threat to dissuade Ásbjörn from

¹⁴ Coles, “The Story of Thórðr Hreða,” 328.

¹⁵ Friðriksson, *Sagan af Þórði Hreðu*, 26.

¹⁶ Coles, “The Story of Thórðr Hreða,” 329-332.

rashly acting on his love of Sigríðr.¹⁷ This exchange, with Ormr setting his head on Sigríðr's lap, has several purposes behind it. The first is purely narrative, as the author is likely trying to get the audience to hate Ormr; this action would have been seen as cowardly and weak. The act of wearing low-cut clothes was an act worthy of divorce in Norse culture, let alone submissively laying one's head on the lap of a woman.¹⁸ Secondly, the interaction shows the author's hatred of fatalism; as Ormr's actions directly infringe on Sigríðr's free will, he compares the idea of a governing destiny to a cowardly man, huddled in the lap of a woman. Ormr's punishment which quickly follows this exchange is more evidence of the author's stance.

What is perhaps more important is the fact that both of these situations are used to teach; the author gives his nuance through these examples, likely as an instruction to the audience. This makes it highly unlikely that the author did not mean for his work to be interpreted in the context of theme, as he dedicated several portions of the saga to those who would do exactly that.

On Rectification

As the introduction briefly touched upon, the author also has a notable affinity for reconciliation, which, while a fairly common event in other works, is taken to extraordinary lengths in this saga. For example, after Ormr was slain by Thórðr, Ormr's kinsmen (namely Skeggi, Indriði, and Össurr) decided to enact revenge upon him. After fleeing Miðfjörðr to escape, Thórðr is pursued by Indriði and four of his friends who ambush him. In the following altercation, Thórðr single-handedly kills the four companions and severely maims Indriði himself. As Indriði lies wounded, rather than leaving him for dead Thórðr decides to take him to Engihlíð where he is healed.¹⁹

¹⁷ Ibid, 324.

¹⁸ Muriel A.C. Press, trans., "Laxdæla Saga," in *The Norse Sagas, Part 2*, vol. 5 (Pounding Mill, VA: Henderson Publishing, 2024), 47-8.

¹⁹ Coles, "The Story of Thórðr Hreða," 335-336.

This act of forgiveness is vanishingly rare; most sagas condone the practice of vengeance, and would see Indriði's death as a thing to be celebrated. Even modern society would not blame Thórðr if he had allowed Indriði to die, as Thórðr would have reason to fear for his life as long as Indriði lives. Making this act of mercy even more astonishing is the context of the brutal warrior civilization to which Thórðr belongs.

In the second example, as Thórðr and nine companions travel to Miklibær they are waylaid by Össurr and a company of eighteen men who intend on killing Thórðr. In the subsequent skirmish Thórðr kills eight men singlehandedly and acutely injures Össurr, while only five of his men die; the remaining nine members of Össurr's band retreat. Thórðr offers to heal Össurr, but he is met with this response: "*Eigi þarftu at bjóða mèt lækning...því at jafnskjótt skal ek drepa þik, sem komumst í færri við þik.*"²⁰ Translated into English, the phrase becomes, 'You do not need to offer me healing...for as soon as I may, I will kill you.' Even though Thórðr knows that Össurr will be a perennial threat to himself as long as he is alive, he chooses to allow Thorgrimr of Ás to heal him.

This act of extreme benevolence is entirely unprecedented in Norse canon. The Norse, known traditionally for their brutality, are in this moment kinder than the vast majority of the modern audience. The comparatively soft expectations of present society would allow for Össurr's death, let alone a warrior civilization that viewed warfare as a common way to earn money.²¹ After he is healed, Össurr makes good on his promise and attacks Thórðr twice more, narrowly surviving the first only to be killed in battle by Thórðr, his patience seemingly exhausted. Although this barrage could be seen as punishment, it is very unlikely that this would be the case. The author would presumably understand that his audience will be difficult to sway,

²⁰ Friðriksson, *Sagan af Þórði Hreðu*, 40.

²¹ Johan Ling, Timothy Earle, and Kristian Kristiansen, "Maritime Mode of Production: Raiding and Trading in Seafaring Chiefdoms," *Current Anthropology* 59, no. 5 (October 2018): 7, <https://doi.org/10.1086/699613>.

and are firmly set into opinions not of his own; therefore, he uses the first example to demonstrate the rewards of his philosophy to begin to persuade his listeners. Now that the audience is already ‘roped-in’, he uses the second example to show that humanitarianism should not require a self-benefiting motivation; that mercy is necessary even if it negatively affects yourself.

The example of Jón and Auðúlfr given earlier is also evidence for the theme of reconciliation. Even though Skeggi and Thórðr had an extremely poor relationship at this point, Skeggi still decided to risk his life by fighting for Thórðr on behalf of Eiðr. This benevolent act is helpful to both Skeggi and Thórðr as the author rewards the characters for their decision; thus, this event lends more credence to the possibility of these proposed themes. The ending of the saga also shows support of both of these themes; the ending, with Thórðr and Skeggi being reconciled, is clear evidence for the theme of forgiveness as the most prominent rivalry in the saga is quelled. The characters are rewarded with their desires; Thórðr marries the widow Thórhallr, Ólöf, while Skeggi lives in peace with Eiðr until his death. Thórðr and Eiðr remain good friends for their lives; each character is well content at the conclusion of the saga.²²

Cultural Synthesis and Implications

Now it must be wondered what effects this interpretation has on the Norse society as a whole; while this one saga is not enough evidence to overthrow the paradigm of their culture, it can add nuance to our current understanding. One of the most well-known facts about Norse culture is their fatalism; a common theme in a number of the most popular sagas (*Brennu-Njáls*

²² Coles, “The Story of Thórðr Hreða”, 326-8, 350-2.

saga, *Laxdæla saga*, and the *Völsunga saga* to name but a few),²³ it has been shown to be a core belief of the Norse.

Fatalism is only one half of the thematic novelty of this saga, with the other half being the unusual importance of mercy. The majority of the sagas are harsh and brutal, and contain passages that are shocking to the modern audience; it appears that the Norse had a taste for violence. Once again, there is a large body of works that support this conclusion; *Völsunga*, *Havamál*, and *Færeyinga saga* all corroborate this, along with many more.²⁴

As has been shown, the saga runs contrary to the motifs found in most other works; this would suggest that the Norse were a fairly open-minded people, willing to understand and appreciate radically different ideas than that which they are used to. This interpretation is supported by the fact that the christianization of Iceland was a mostly peaceful yet tedious process; it has been argued that their polytheistic religion made them susceptible to conversion, as they would have little difficulty in accepting new gods.²⁵ This is evidenced by the fact that Christianity and Norse Paganism coexisted for a time; it was not uncommon for a person to believe in the existence of both at once, although the pagan deities would be demoted to demons in such cases. Olaf Tryggvason reportedly met Odin, and it was said in the *Njála* that Jesus had refused a duel with Thor.²⁶ The themes of *Þórðar saga hreðu* serve as good evidence for this

²³ George DaSent, trans., *The Story of Burnt Njál* (Edinburgh: Edmonston and Douglas, 1861), <https://tinyurl.com/y3b4cz5v>; Press, “Laxdæla Saga”, 44; Morris and Magnusson, “The Saga of the Völsungs,” 41; “Explore: ‘Njál’s saga,’ ‘Völsunga saga,’ ‘Laxdæla saga,’ ‘Eyrbyggja saga,’ ‘Egil’s saga,’ ‘Grettis saga,’ ‘Tale of Ragnar Lodbrok,’ Worldwide, 2004-Present,” Google Trends, Google, accessed February 13, 2026, [<https://tinyurl.com/2u6ews39>].

²⁴ Morris and Magnusson, “The Saga of the Völsungs,” 4-8; Henry Bellows, trans., “Hovamol: The Ballad of the High One,” in *The Poetic Eddas*, 1st ed. (New York, NY: The American-Scandinavian Foundation, 1936), 28–9, <https://tinyurl.com/bde49v3c>; Fredrick Powell, trans., “The Saga of Thron of Gate,” in *The Norse Sagas, Part 3*, vol. 6 (1896; repr., Pounding Mill, VA: Henderson Publishing, 2024), 116.

²⁵ Hjalti Hugason, *Frumkristni og upphaf kirkju*, ed. Hjalti Hugason, vol. 1 (Reykjavík: Alþingi, 2000), quoted in Steinunn Kristjánsdóttir, “The Awakening of Christianity in Iceland: Discovery of a Timber Church and Graveyard at Þórarinsstaðir in Seyðisfjörður,” *Academia.edu*, 2004, 8-9, <https://tinyurl.com/jabwzede>.

²⁶ Annette Lassen, “Óðinn in Old Norse Texts Other than ‘the Elder Edda’, ‘Snorra Edda’, and ‘Ynglinga Saga,’” *Viking and Medieval Scandinavia* 1 (2005), 95-6, <https://tinyurl.com/46s7x9yc>; DaSent, *The Story of Burnt Njál*, 135.

idea; as the saga was fairly popular in its contemporary time, the Norse audience which enjoyed it must not have had any severe dislike of the themes.²⁷

Yet, these implications are not only of scholarly concern. The relatively peaceful Christianization process in Iceland is an exception; most Christianization happened via conquest, as the victor would impose beliefs upon their new domain.²⁸ Even other Norse countries had violent pushback to early attempts to Christianize them; Olaf Tryggvason had burned soothsayers alive to enforce his religion.²⁹ The fact that the Christianization of Iceland was mostly peaceful is an important point in history. If the issue was not peacefully resolved at the Alþing, the ensuing war may have swallowed the whole country; Thorgeir, the ‘law-speaker’ who decided the case, said that “it was a reasonable expectation that armed conflicts would arise among men such that the land would be wasted.”³⁰ A state riddled with war would have little time for other pursuits; their raiding, trading and seafaring would have slowed drastically, limiting their influence on the outside world. Norway could very well have interfered in the war against them, as they were being pressured by Olaf Tryggvason to Christianize,³¹ if Norway joined, their influence on the world would be dampened as well, potentially redefining the Viking-Age itself. These themes help explain a paradigm that changed Europe.

²⁷ Ward, “Completing Þórðr Saga Hreðu: A Regional Saga in Disguise,” 1.

²⁸ Lloyd Steffen, “Religion and Violence in Christian Traditions,” *The Oxford Handbook of Religion and Violence*, March 12, 2013, 102, <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199759996.013.0005>.

²⁹ Haki Antonsson, “Traditions of Conversion in Medieval Scandinavia: A Synthesis,” *Saga-Book* 34 (2010): 40, <https://tinyurl.com/3xtkjk28>.

³⁰ Ari Þorgilsson, *Íslendingabók*, as quoted in William Miller, “Of Outlaws, Christians, Horsemeat, and Writing: Uniform Laws and Saga Iceland,” *Michigan Law Review* 89 (August 1991): 2090, <https://repository.law.umich.edu/facarticles/205/>.

³¹ Orri Vésteinsson, “The Conversion of the Icelanders,” in *Europe around the Year 1000*, ed. Przemysław Urbańczyk, 1st ed. (Warsaw: Institute of Archaeology and Ethnology, Polish Academy of Sciences, 2001), 325, <https://tinyurl.com/5de62vn7>.

Conclusion

As this essay has shown, *Þórðar saga hreðu* is an exception to the generally seen themes in the Norse sagas. It is both libertarian and humanist, despite the fact that the antithesis to these themes is commonly seen in accompanying works. The refrain in the saga is strong proof of the libertarian portion, especially when coupled with the common writing techniques that are present in most other Norse literature. The fact that the author spends a portion of the story ‘teaching’ the audience through the cases of Auðúlfr/Jón and Ormr strongly implies that these conclusions were meant to be drawn about it. The humanist part is supported by the merciful actions of Thórðr towards Össur and Indriði, which were extremely uncommon in that time frame. These interactions are solid evidence for the conclusions this essay has drawn. It was shown to be very unusual for the time frame, as most of the other works are strongly against these motifs; this would imply that the Icelanders were very open-minded as the saga was fairly popular, therefore making it unlikely that the audience detested the themes.³²

This gives an explanation for why the Christianization of Iceland was so peaceful, as the Icelanders were open to ideas different from their own; if the Christianization were not so mild, the Norse states could very well have been torn apart via infighting. If the Norse were fighting against themselves (more than they already were), would the raids that defined the later Viking Age have been so strong or influential? Would history follow the same path? Humanity will only be able to speculate, but all the evidence points to ‘no’.

³² Ward, “Completing Þórðar saga hreðu”, 1.

Bibliography

- Bellows, Henry, trans. “Hovamol: The Ballad of the High One.” In *The Poetic Eddas*, 1st ed., 28–67. New York, NY: The American-Scandinavian Foundation, 1936.
<https://tinyurl.com/bde49v3c>.
- Cleasby, Richard, and Guðbrandur Vigfússon. “Ei-Gi, Munu, Göra, Sem, Þér, Líka, Of-Láti.” In *An Icelandic-English Dictionary*. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1874.
<https://tinyurl.com/mx33vcu9>.
- Coles, John, trans. “The Saga of Thórðr Hreða.” In *The Norse Sagas, Part 1*, 4:316–52. 1882. Reprint, Pounding Mill, VA: Henderson Publishing, 2024.
- DaSent, George, trans. *The Story of Burnt Njál*. Edinburgh: Edmonston and Douglas, 1861.
<https://tinyurl.com/y3b4cz5v>.
- Friðriksson, H, trans. *Sagan Af Þórði Hreðu*. Vol. VI. Copenhagen: Brødrene Berlings Bogtrykkeri, 1848.
- Griffith, Tom, ed. *Njál's Saga*. Translated by Carl F. Bayerschmidt and Lee M. Hollander. *Njál's Saga*. Ware, Hertfordshire: Wordsworth Classics of World Literature, 1998.
- Halldórsson, Jóhannes, ed. *Íslendinga Sögur XI: Kjalnesinga Saga, Þórðar Saga Hreðu, Finnboga Saga Ramma*. Reykjavík: Hið íslenska fornritafélag, 1959.
- Head, Edmund, trans. “The Saga of Víga-Glum.” In *The Norse Sagas, Part 1*, 4:397–445. 1866. Reprint, Pounding Mill, VA: Henderson Publishing, 2024.
- Hugason, Hjalti. *Frumkristni Og Upphaf Kirkju*. Edited by Hjalti Hugason. Vol. 1. Reykjavík: Alþingi, 2000.
- Kristjánsdóttir, Steinunn. “The Awakening of Christianity in Iceland Discovery of a Timber Church and Graveyard at Þórarinsstaðir in Seyðisfjörður.” *Academia.edu*, 2004.
<https://tinyurl.com/jabwzede>.
- Lassen, Annette. “Óðinn in Old Norse Texts Other than ‘the Elder Edda’, ‘Snorra Edda’, and ‘Ynglinga Saga.’” *Viking and Medieval Scandinavia* 1 (2005): 91–108.
<https://tinyurl.com/46s7x9yc>.

- Ling, Johan, Timothy Earle, and Kristian Kristiansen. “Maritime Mode of Production: Raiding and Trading in Seafaring Chiefdoms.” *Current Anthropology* 59, no. 5 (October 2018): 488–524. <https://doi.org/10.1086/699613>.
- Morris, William, and Eiríkr Magnússon, trans. “The Saga of the Völsungs.” In *The Norse Sagas, Part 1*, 4:1–78. 1888. Reprint, Pounding Mill, VA: Henderson Publishing, 2024.
- Powell, Fredrick, trans. “The Saga of Thronð of Gate.” In *The Norse Sagas, Part 3*, 6:108–72. 1896. Reprint, Pounding Mill, VA: Henderson Publishing, 2024.
- Press, Muriel A.C., trans. “Laxdæla Saga.” In *The Norse Sagas, Part 2*, 5:1–120. Pounding Mill, VA: Henderson Publishing, 2024.
- Stefánsson, Jón, and William Collingwood, trans. “The Life and Death of Cormac the Skald.” In *The Norse Sagas, Part 3*, 6:36–60. 1902. Reprint, Pounding Mill, VA: Henderson Publishing, 2024.
- Sturluson, Snorri. “Heimskringla, by Snorri Sturlason.” Project Gutenberg, November 27, 2009. <https://tinyurl.com/7ymbct5v>.
- Ward, Elizabeth. “Completing Þórðar Saga Hreðu.” *Gripla* 27, no. 1 (2016). <https://tinyurl.com/hd4eakex>.